

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE STABILITY OF ETHYLENE DIBIGUANIDE COMPLEX OF TRIPOSITIVE SILVER

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The stability of ethylenedibiguanide complex of tripositive silver in aqueous solution has been determined from the equilibrium constant of the reaction between the complex and the hydrogen ion, and the acid dissociation constants of the base ethylenedibiguanide. The equilibrium constant was derived from a knowledge of the p_w value of the acid solution containing the complex and of the concentration of Ag^{3+} ion therein. The latter was derived from the measurement of redox potential of the acid solution of the complex salt in presence of Ag^+ ion and ethylenedibiguanide. The value obtained for the instability constant was found to be of the order of 10^{-52} , representing a very high degree of stability for the complex, as against 10^{-34} for the cobaltamines, and approaches that of cobaltic *tris*-biguanide complex (10^{-55}) determined by De, Ghosh and Rây (previous communication).

The occurrence of tripositive silver has been proved by Luther and Pokorny (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 57, 290), as also by Carman (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 566). This has been supported fully by the preparation of many complex compounds of tripositive silver in pure state by Malaprade (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1935, v, 2, 359; 1936, 3, 361; 1938, 5, 582; *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 979), Malatesta (*Gazzetta*, 1941, 71, 467, 480) and by Rây and Chakravarty (*this Journal*, 1944, 21, 47).

The present work deals with the determination of the stability of a well established tripositive silver complex of ethylenedibiguanide, prepared in this laboratory (Rây and Chakravarty, *loc. cit.*). The substance forms an inner metallic complex of the third order (Rây and Dutt, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 563) with quite a high degree of stability; its nitrate in nitric acid solution (dil.) can be heated almost to boiling without any appreciable decomposition. The ethylenedibiguanide behaves as a quadridentate ligand and the tripositive silver shows a co-ordination number of four. Each silver atom is bound by two primary and two secondary valencies to the ethylenedibiguanide molecule, which latter binds again two hydrogen ions. The substance therefore presents many interesting features of study.

The dissociation of the silver ethylenedibiguanide complex may be represented by the following equation :

where $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2 =$ a molecule of ethylenedibiguanide =

Therefore,

$$K = \text{the instability constant} = \frac{[\text{Ag}^{3+}] \times [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^{\pm})_2]}{[\text{Ag} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2]^{+++}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

In order to obtain K , the equilibrium constant K' of the decomposition reaction, given below, has to be first determined :

$$\text{Hence } K' = \frac{[\text{Ag}^{3+}] \times [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2]}{[\text{Ag} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2]^{+++} \times [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Ethylenedibiguanide can at most behave as a tetra-acidic base, and its acid dissociation constants k_1^* , k_2^* , k_3^* , and k_4^* are given by :

$$\text{Therefore, } k_1^* = \frac{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[(\text{BigH}) \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_2)_2]} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } k_2^* = \frac{[(\text{BigH}) \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_2)_2] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2]} \quad \dots \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{Therefore } k_3^* = \frac{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[(\text{BigH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_3^{++})]} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } k_4^* = \frac{[(\text{BigH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_3^{++})] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_3^{++})_2]} \quad \dots \quad (4a)$$

Now from (3) and (3a),

$$[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2] = \frac{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2 \times [\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*},$$

combining this with (2) we get, the instability constant $K = K' \cdot k_1^* \cdot k_2^*$.

The equilibrium constant, K' , can be determined by knowing $[\text{Ag}^{3+}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Ag} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2]^{+++}$. Of these, $[\text{H}^+]$ ion can be obtained by measuring the pH of the solution and $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2]$ from the following relation.

Let x be the total biguanide added, then

$$x = [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_3^{++})_2] + [(\text{BigH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_3^{++})] + [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}_2)_2]$$

{neglecting $[(\text{BigH})_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{BigH}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2]$, as the measurements were made in acid solutions}.

Therefore, from (4) and (4a),

$$x = [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 (\text{BigH}_2)_2] \left(1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_3} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_3 \cdot k_4} \right)$$

Hence, $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 (\text{BigH}_2)_2] = \frac{x \cdot k_3 \cdot k_4}{k_3 \cdot k_4 + k_4 \cdot [\text{H}^+] + [\text{H}^+]^2} \dots \dots (5)$

Now, in order to find out $[\text{Ag}^{3+}]$, the oxidation potential of the complex silver ethylenedibiguanide nitrate in presence of Ag^+ ion and ethylenedibiguanide ion in acid and water solution was determined against a saturated calomel electrode. From this, provided that the normal redox potential of the argentic (III)—argentous (I) system is known, the concentration of the Ag^{3+} ion in a solution of the complex salt can be calculated from the well known equation :

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}}{a_{\text{Ag}^+}} \dots \dots (6)$$

where E is the observed E.M.F., corrected to normal hydrogen electrode; E_0 , standard electrode potential for argentic (III)—argentous (I) system, and $n=2$; $a_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}$ and a_{Ag^+} are the activities of Ag^{3+} and Ag^+ ions in solution, which become practically equal to their respective concentrations in dilute solutions. The value of E_0 , however, is not definitely known, nor is its determination easy. It was, however, approximated from the E.M.F. of the following cell, measured by Luther and Pokorny (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 57, 290) at 25°.

If it be permitted to assume that the normal electrode potential of argentic (III)—argentous (I) system does not vary to any great extent from the above value of 1.74 volts, then the value of Ag^{3+} -concentration can be computed from the equation. As the temperature coefficient of electrode potentials is generally of the order of 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} , the value of E_0 at the temperature of the experiment has been recalculated with the temperature coefficient value of +0.0017 in analogy with that of the $\text{Co}^{3+} - \text{Co}^{2+}$ system (Lamb and Larson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2024).

It should, however, be pointed out here that Noyes and Kossakoff (*ibid.*, 1935, 57, 1238) obtained a normal oxidation potential of 1.914 volts for the system consisting of unipositive and bipoisitive silver ions in nitric acid solution. Noyes and co-workers have further shown that the bipoisitive silver ion in aqueous solution changes more or less rapidly by dismutation into tripositive and unipositive silver ions :

This seems to suggest that tripositive silver is more stable than its bipoisitive state. We may therefore with some justification adopt the value, +1.74 volts, as the redox potential for $\text{Ag}^{3+} - \text{Ag}^+$ system, and that will give us a maximum limit for the instability constant K of the complex.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of the Solutions

Ethylenedibiguanide Nitrate.—Ethylenedibiguanide acid sulphate was prepared and purified by recrystallisation from hot water containing a little sulphuric acid (Rây and Chakravarty, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 41). (Found : SO_4 , 42.64. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_{10}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 42.57 per cent).

The sulphate (2.2602 g.) was taken in a 500 c.c. volumetric flask. A little water was added to this and then 20 c.c. of a 0.5*N*-KOH solution were added from a burette. Most of the substance went into solution leaving a small residue. The flask was then heated on the water-bath till a clear solution was obtained. A calculated quantity of *M*/5- $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution (50 c.c.) was next added to it from a burette. The precipitated BaSO_4 was allowed to settle overnight. The volume was made up to 501 c.c. (allowing 1c.c. for the volume of the precipitate). The solution, which was free from Ba^{++} and SO_4^{--} ions, was then filtered. The strength of the nitrate ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_{10}\cdot 2\text{HNO}_3$) solution, thus prepared, was *M*/100.

Silver Nitrate Solution.—A *M*/50-solution was prepared from a double-recrystallised sample of silver nitrate (Analar quality) ; 0.6794 g. of the substance was dissolved in water and the volume made up to 200 c.c.

Potassium Nitrate Solution.—A 2*M* solution was prepared by dissolving 40.44 g. of potassium nitrate (Kahlbaum reagent) in 200c.c. of conductivity water.

Nitric Acid.—Chemically pure nitric acid was distilled in an all-glass apparatus. The first fraction contained some brown nitrous fumes and was rejected. The clear acid then distilling over was collected in a dry amber coloured bottle. The distillation was stopped before the whole of the acid distilled over. From this acid a 1.5*N* solution was prepared by checking with titration against sodium carbonate. From this latter, other solutions of weaker strength were prepared by necessary dilution.

Silver Ethylenedibiguanide Nitrate.—The complex nitrate was prepared and purified by recrystallisation from hot 2*N*- HNO_3 , following the procedure described by Rây and Chakravarty (*loc. cit.*). {Found : Ag, 20.62, 20.69 ; Ag^{3+} , 20.69. [$\text{Ag}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2$](NO_3)₃ requires Ag, 20.69 ; Ag^{3+} , 20.69 per cent}.

In all the determinations a Beckmann p_{H} -meter (model G) was used for the measurement of E. M. F. and p_{H} values.

Determination of the Oxidation Potential

A standard calomel electrode supplied with the apparatus was used as the reference electrode. This was not, however, directly dipped into the solution under examination, but was connected to the latter by a bridge liquid of KNO_3 ($2M$) solution in order to reduce the liquid junction potential. The arrangement of the bridge was as follows: The calomel electrode was dipped into $2M\text{-KNO}_3$ solution in a vessel, which had a capillary tube fused at its bottom that served to connect the liquid under examination with the calomel electrode. The platinum electrode in the case of potential measurement and glass electrode in the case of p_{H} measurement were dipped directly into the solution under examination. All the measurements were made after waiting for 10 to 15 minutes for equilibrium to be attained at the room temperature. Solution of the complex salt for each measurement was freshly prepared from the solid crystals.

The results of the experiments are arranged in the following tables. E (corrected) refers to the E. M. F. corrected to standard hydrogen electrode. The values of k^*_1 , k^*_2 , k^*_3 , and k^*_4 , or their p_k values were taken from the work of B. Sarma (unpublished). These were determined by the measurement of p_{H} values of a solution of ethylenedibiguanide when progressively titrated with an acid.

TABLE I

$C_{\text{Ag}^+} = 0.0008M$. Total ethylenedibiguanide = $0.0008M$. $t = 31^\circ$.

$E_0 = 1.751$ volt. $p_k^*_1 = 11.76$; $p_k^*_2 = 11.34$; $p_k^*_3 = 2.88$; $p_k^*_4 = 1.74$

Complex.	p_{H} .	E (corr.).	$C_{\text{B}} \times 10^3$.	$C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}$	p_{K} .	p_{Kc} .
0.0032M	3.47	0.9669	63.39	7.13×10^{-20}	46.01	52.95
0.0016	3.67	0.9479	68.69	1.67×10^{-20}	45.90	53.21
0.0008	3.87	0.9279	72.47	35.74×10^{-22}	45.85	53.62
0.0004	4.00	0.9099	74.29	9.18×10^{-22}	45.87	53.87
0.0002	4.08	0.8939	75.25	2.71×10^{-22}	45.93	54.09
0.0001	4.30	0.8799	77.23	9.18×10^{-23}	45.65	54.25

p_{Kc} (mean) = 53.67

TABLE II

$C_{AG^+} = 0.0008M$. Total ethylenedibiguanide = 0.0008M. $t = 32^\circ$.
 $C_{\text{complex}} = 0.0008M$. $E_0 = 1.752$ volt. $pK_1^* = 11.76$; $pK_2^* = 11.34$;
 $pK_3^* = 2.88$; $pK_4^* = 1.74$.

Acid.	pH.	E (corr.).	$C_B \times 10^5$.	$C_{AG^{3+}}$	pK.	pKc.
0.200M	0.82	1.045	0.075	0.032×10^{-26}	50.99	52.63
0.100	1.11	1.038	0.257	0.019×10^{-26}	50.10	52.32
0.050	1.40	1.030	0.822	0.101×10^{-26}	49.28	52.08
0.020	1.78	1.014	3.192	0.290×10^{-27}	48.48	52.04
0.010	2.01	1.006	6.445	1.596×10^{-28}	47.97	52.00
0.005	2.29	0.990	13.360	4.710×10^{-29}	47.62	52.20
0.002	2.71	0.967	30.320	8.375×10^{-30}	47.18	52.38
						pKc (mean) = 52.26

TABLE III

$C_{AG^+} = 0.0008M$. $C_{\text{complex}} = 0.0008M$. $C_{HNO_3} = 0.025M$. $t = 35^\circ$.
 $E_0 = 1.757$ volt. $pK_1^* = 11.76$; $pK_2^* = 11.34$, $pK_3^* = 2.88$; $pK_4^* = 1.74$.

Et-dibiguanide.	pH.	E (corr.).	$C_B \times 10^5$.	$C_{AG^{3+}}$.	pK.	pKc.
0.0060 M	1.76	0.988	20.910	0.475×10^{-28}	48.49	52.01
0.0032	1.76	0.994	11.950	0.753×10^{-28}	48.53	52.05
0.0016	1.74	0.999	5.594	1.104×10^{-28}	48.73	52.21
0.0008	1.73	1.006	2.705	1.888×10^{-29}	48.84	52.30
0.0004	1.71	1.010	1.248	2.559×10^{-29}	49.08	52.50
0.0002	1.70	1.013	0.613	3.157×10^{-29}	49.32	52.72
						pKc (mean) = 52.30

TABLE IV

$C_{AG^+} = 0.0008M$. Total ethylenedibiguanide = 0.0008M. $t = 32^\circ$. $C_{HNO_3} = 0.05M$
 $E_0 = 1.752$ volt. $pK_1^* = 11.76$; $pK_2^* = 11.34$; $pK_3^* = 2.88$; $pK_4^* = 1.74$.

Complex.	pH.	E (corr.).	$C_B \times 10^5$.	$C_{AG^{3+}}$.	pK.	pKc.
0.0032M	1.38	1.040	0.7614	21.23×10^{-28}	49.64	52.40
0.0016	1.38	1.035	0.7614	14.55×10^{-28}	49.50	52.26
0.0008	1.39	1.029	0.7914	9.18×10^{-28}	49.36	52.14
0.0004	1.39	1.022	0.7914	5.41×10^{-28}	49.29	52.07
0.0002	1.40	1.013	0.8230	2.71×10^{-28}	49.25	52.05
0.0001	1.40	1.004	0.8230	1.37×10^{-28}	49.25	52.05
						pKc (mean) = 52.16

DISCUSSION

From an examination of the tables, particularly Table II, it will be observed that the p_K values decrease with the rise of the p_H values of the solution containing the complex. This seems to suggest that stability of the complex increases with the acid concentration of the solution. This is apparently supported by the general behaviour of a solution of the silver ethylenedibiguanide nitrate which can be boiled in 2*N*-HNO₃ solution without any noticeable change. In fact, the substance is purified, as already described, by recrystallisation from dilute nitric acid solution. But a distinction should be made between the decomposition and dissociation of the complex. It is the decomposition of the complex which is actually retarded by the hydrogen ion, whereas dissociation constant should have remained constant under all conditions, if all our assumptions were correct. The tripositive silver ion is, however, more or less unstable and in aqueous solution breaks down possibly as follows:

So, in the determination of the redox potential for Ag³⁺—Ag⁺ system, the above reaction should preferably be taken into consideration in place of the simple $\text{Ag}^{3+} + 2e \rightleftharpoons \text{Ag}^+$, as assumed for the calculation of $C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}$ and p_K values of the tables.

A recalculation of $C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}$ and p_K values on this basis gives more or less a constant p_K value in each table for the temperature of measurement. These are denoted by the symbol p_{Kc} , i.e. p_K corrected. The p_{Kc} values can, however, be readily obtained from p_K values by the use of the expression

$$p_{Kc} = p_K + 2p_H.$$

For, $\ln \frac{C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}}{C_{\text{Ag}^+}}$ in the equation for E.M.F. is to be substituted by

$$\ln \frac{C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}}{C_{\text{Ag}^+} \times [\text{H}^+]^2}.$$

Hence the value of $C_{\text{Ag}^{3+}}$ in our equation (1) for the instability constant, K , will be $[\text{H}^+]^2$ times the value employed before.

These p_{Kc} values have been added as a separate column in each table at the end. This brings to a closer agreement among values in all other tables excepting those in Table I, ignoring, however, the slight differences of temperature. The individual p_{Kc} values in Table I also differ somewhat largely among themselves. This may be attributed to two causes: (a) hydrolysis of the complex, salt in solutions of low acidity giving rise to basic cations; (b) increased tendency of the tripositive silver ion, Ag³⁺, to break up into Ag⁺, H⁺ and oxygen gas rendering the redox reaction at

the electrode rather more or less irreversible. Hydrolysis of the complex salt occurs as follows :

Further hydrolysis may lead to a still basic ion, $[\text{Ag. C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{LigH})_2]^{+}(\text{OH})_2$. So, the concentration of the pure complex ion is thereby altered. In solutions of moderately low p_{H} values this salt hydrolysis of the complex is more or less completely retarded. The p_{Kc} value for the silver ethylene-dibiguanide complex may thus be regarded as approximately equal to 52, representing, so to say, its maximum range of instability. The extraordinary stability of this inner complex of tripositive silver is hereby established, in keeping with its general behaviour. The value of its instability constant approaches closely that of the *tris*-biguanide cobaltic complex (10^{-55} approx.) described previously by De, Ghosh and Ray (this *Journal* 1950, 27, 493), and is considerably smaller than that of the cobaltammines investigated by Lamb and Larson (*loc. cit.*), which are of the order of 10^{-34} .

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